

Paediatric Endodontics (Part 2)

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The pulp of primary teeth possesses the ability to form a dentin-like matrix (tertiary dentin) as part of the repair mechanism of the dentin-pulp complex. Vital pulp therapy procedures (or indirect capping) aim to treat reversible pulpal injury due to caries, restorative procedures, or trauma. It is considered nowadays an acceptable procedure based on good history and proper clinical and radiographic examination. It should be followed by a good restoration. We must keep in mind that the direct pulp treatment procedures are less predictable as failure is likely to occur in case of even a minute pulp exposure. So the procedures have to be carried out under rubber dam isolation, free from oral contaminants. Such teeth should preferably be treated by procedures like pulpotomy or pulpectomy.

Pulpotomy

The American Academy of Paediatric Dentistry defines pulpotomy as the ablation of infected or affected pulp tissues leaving the residual vital pulp tissues intact, thus preserving vitality and function (totally or partially) of the radicular pulp, and the remaining pulp stump is covered with a capping agent. The only difference between pulp capping and vital pulpotomy resides in the quantity of pulp tissue that is removed. In case of vital pulpotomy on permanent teeth, an agent allowing the cauterization of the amputated site is used such as calcium hydroxide. However, the success of this procedure is stated to be low and is conditioned by 3 factors:

1. The tooth must be in stage I (roots still in formation).
2. The trauma relative to the operatory procedure must be minimal.
3. A high-pH calcium hydroxide must be used.

The success of the treatment is measured by the absence of clinical symptoms such as pain or oedema, the absence of radiologic symptoms such as internal resorption or intracanal calcifications, the absence of periodontal involvement, and finally the preservation of the integrity of the tooth bud.

Theoretically, following the access opening and total removal of the roof, the tissue in the pulp chamber must be completely excised all the way to the pulp stumps or the coronal opening of the canal. In fact, the level to which the pulpotomy is performed is best left to the clinical judgment of the operator since all inflammation has to be removed to allow the placement of the medication on sound pulp tissues. Several studies have

confirmed that when the pulp exposure is traumatic (fracture) or iatrogenic (following cavity preparation), the inflammation is confined to the superficial layer (1-2mm) without bacterial infiltration. Whereas when the carious lesions are extensive and are in direct bacterial contact with the pulp, inflammation is present between 1 and 9mm from the surface with abscess and pus formation.

Many agents were used in pulpotomy procedures over the years. Glutaraldehyde, electrosurgery, lasers, ferric sulphate, collagen, freeze-dried bone, morphogenetic bone proteins, and MTA (Mineral Trioxide Aggregate) are among these alternatives. Evidence is still lacking to determine which agent is the most appropriate for pulpotomies in primary teeth.

Indications

Vital pulpotomy (calcium hydroxide, MTA) is indicated in case of minimal iatrogenic pulp exposure and in case of stage I primary teeth and in permanent teeth. Non-vital pulpotomy is indicated for pulp exposure of primary teeth where inflammation/infection is limited to the coronal portion of the pulp.

Contra-indications

Contra-indications of pulpotomy include unrestorable teeth, teeth nearing exfoliation, absence of bone between the temporary tooth and the erupting permanent tooth, radicular resorption reaching the cervical third, spontaneous pain, presence of periodontal lesions, absence of bleeding when opening the access cavity, uncontrollable haemorrhage after pulp amputation, presence of purulent or serous drainage, or presence of fistulous tract.

Procedure

After anaesthesia and rubber dam isolation, complete carious lesion is removed with a high-speed handpiece. The pulp chamber roof is removed and the entire pulpal tissue is eliminated using a low-speed handpiece under spray or with a sharp excavator. Eliminating these tissues has to be complete otherwise haemorrhage would be uncontrollable. The cavity is rinsed with water then dried with cotton pellets. Haemostasis is obtained by compressing the cotton pellets against the pulp stumps in the canal orifices. Haemostasis is normally performed in 4-5 minutes. Failure to achieve it in on time is a sign that inflammation is deeper than suspected, in which case the tooth is

not treatable by pulpotomy and the only remaining therapeutic option is pulpectomy. When the cotton pellet is removed, tissues should not show any signs of bleeding. Zinc-oxide eugenol cements can be used to seal the canal openings, covered by a glass-ionomer filling. After setting, composite materials can be used to restore the tooth.

Postoperative follow-up

The failure of a pulpotomy treatment is generally detected radiographically. First signs are generally internal root resorption facing the point of application of fixative agent. It can later be followed by an external resorption. Radiolucent areas develop at the furcation level, at the apex, or laterally on the roots. A fistula may be present and the tooth becomes mobile however, pain is a rare occurrence in failing pulpotomy.

Pulpectomy

When the tooth cannot be treated by pulpotomy or in certain failing pulpotomy cases, pulpectomy is the last resort before extraction. To ensure the success of the root canal treatment on deciduous teeth, the practitioner must be familiar with the mode of formation of their roots as well as the variations that might occur in their root canal system. Always remember that the radicular genesis is complete 3-4 years after tooth eruption. The roots of deciduous teeth are more divergent than that of their permanent counterparts which makes space for the bud of the permanent tooth. The phenomena of radicular resorption and dentine apposition on the surface of the canal modify considerably the aspect and the number of canals. It should be stressed that most variations are in the buccolingual direction and that radiography only show mesiodistal anatomy. Hence the position of the main apical foramina that is located at the root vertex may often be more coronal. This anatomophysiological characteristic is the cause of radiographic working length errors that can lead to overextension of the shaping instrumentation and overfills that may in turn harm the underlying bud of the permanent tooth. Radicular resorption of the deciduous tooth may create pulpoperiodontal communications far more extended than the apical foramen.

Indications

Pulpectomy is indicated in case of acute pulp inflammation leading to an uncontrollable haemorrhage after pulpotomy, in case of trauma on anterior primary or permanent teeth involving the pulp tissue, and in cases of necrosis and/or periodontal lesions.

Contra-indications

They are generally linked to the overall health of the child (special needs, disabled or cardiac patients), or to clinical considerations such as severely broken down teeth, unrestorable teeth, complex root canal morphology, internal or external resorptions, physiological resorption involving more than 2/3 of the root, perforated pulp floor with or without pathological bone resorption.

Procedure

The pulpectomy technique in itself is rather similar to that performed on the permanent tooth. Following the administration of anaesthesia and placing the rubber dam, the access cavity is performed and the roof of the pulp chamber is removed. All overhanging dentin should be removed. Shaping and cleaning are the heart of the endodontic treatment just like the permanent teeth. Estimated root canal length is obtained using a preliminary radiograph and subtracting 1-2mm from the length of the root canal as seen on the radiograph; it is then adjusted by placing a file to the actual length and confirming radiographically. Because of their electrical and morphophysiological characteristics electronic working length determination is not possible in deciduous teeth. It is often preferable to reduce working length by 1-2mm to avoid over-instrumentation and overfilling as these teeth are often prone to apical resorption, and preserving the integrity of the apical area is most important. In general, wide canals (incisors and canines) are shaped to #25. Shaping is done in the conventional manner (step-back) while avoiding ultrasonic instrumentation to preserve the relatively thin root canal walls. Nickel-titanium rotary instruments are ideal for shaping deciduous teeth. Irrigation is more crucial for cleaning since shaping is kept to a minimum and we rely on chemical cleaning to reach areas that cannot be addressed by mechanical instrumentation. Using 5.25% sodium hypochlorite combined to 17% aqueous EDTA is capable of cleaning most complexities and irregularities of the root canal system. Contrary to permanent teeth, filling materials used for root canal sealing of deciduous teeth should be resorbable so they can be eliminated during the physiological root resorption process and not interfere the eruption of the permanent tooth. Hence after cleaning and shaping, root canals are rinsed a last time with sodium hypochlorite, dried with paper points, and filled using a zinc oxide-eugenol paste and packed in the access cavity using a wet cotton pellet. Overfilling should be avoided. The coronal access is then sealed using a glass ionomer and a preformed metallic stainless steel paedodontic crown is placed to avoid tooth fracture.

Postoperative follow-up

Follow-up is indicated with criteria for clinical success being no mobility, pain, fistula or abscess; and criteria for radiologic success being no pathological resorption and no radiolucency.

Conclusion

The success of the endodontic treatment on deciduous teeth cannot be achieved without knowledge and understanding of pulp morphology, root genesis and resorptive processes related to deciduous teeth. Following the rational fundamentals in case selection and operative techniques, paediatric endodontics remains a major benefit to the child's health and wellbeing.